

Solvent free synthesis of new-1-acetyl-3-(4-fluoronaphthyl)-5-substituted aryl pyrazolines as spermicides

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Abstract : In this paper we wish to report the solvent free synthesis of 1-acetyl-3-(4-fluoronaphthyl)-5-substituted aryl pyrazolines by using simple and efficient Green Chemistry techniques (Grindstone method and microwave irradiation). These methods have been developed for the rapid solvent free synthesis of title compounds from corresponding chalcones and hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine in acetic acid. Considerable increase in the reaction rates have been observed with better yields compared with sample prepared from conventional method. Structure of synthesized new compounds have been confirmed on the basis of spectral (IR, ^1H NMR) and analytical data. Representative compounds have been screened for their spermicidal activity in HF cattles and Murrah buffalo.

Keywords : Aldol condensation, chalcone, pyrazoline, Grindstone chemistry, microwave irradiation.

Introduction

Non-steroidal heterocycles as antifertility agents have been reviewed by Pathak *et al.*¹. The pyrazole nucleus is reported to possess contraceptive and abortifacient activities²⁻⁴. Pyrazoline derivatives were synthesized and screened as antifertility agents by Sangwan and Rastogi⁵ but none of these compounds could prevent pregnancy at a dose of 10 mg/kg. Keeping in view the observation that the introduction of fluorine leads to altered biological activity in many systems, we thought it worthwhile to incorporate fluorine into pyrazoline system and study whether this would lead to better antifertility activity.

The chemistry of chalcones has aroused great interest due to their pharmaceutical activities i.e. antibacterial, antifungal⁶, antiallergic⁷, antiproliferative⁸, antitubercular⁹, antitumor¹⁰, antiinflammatory¹¹, antileishmanial and antifertility activities. The substituted fluorinated chalcones were prepared by base catalysed aldol condensation of fluorinated ketone/PTSA, and substituted aldehydes. Aldol condensation reactions is widely used in synthetic organic chemistry and is important C-C bond forming reaction¹³⁻¹⁵.

The increasing application of microwave irradiation as source of thermal energy in organic reaction is due to the short reaction time and operational simplicity¹⁶. In last few years microwave induced organic reaction en-

hancement (MORE) chemistry is gaining popularity as a non-conventional technique for rapid organic synthesis^{17,18}. In Grindstone chemistry, reactions are initiated by grinding with transfer of very small amount of energy through friction, the reaction proceeds itself if it is exothermic in nature. Conversely, if the reaction is endothermic grinding will not make the reaction go forward¹⁹. No heating and no organic solvent is utilized in the grinding procedure. Single cross aldol condensation products are produced in high yields even in reactions where a mixture of product is possible²⁰.

In view of above observation we have used conventional and solvent free synthetic methods (Grindstone method and microwave irradiation) for synthesis of new substituted chalcones and pyrazoline derivatives. The required starting material 1-(4-fluoronaphthyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-propen-1-ones (**2a-f**) were prepared by treatment of equimolar amount of 4-fluoro-acetonaphthone substituted phenyl and substituted aryl aldehyde in presence of a catalyst (PTSA, $\text{Mg}(\text{HSO}_4)_2$, K-10). The final product 1-acetyl-3-(4-fluoronaphthyl)-5-substituted aryl pyrazolines (**3a-f**) were synthesized by cycloaddition of compounds (**2a-f**) with hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine in presence of glacial acetic acid under microwave irradiation (Scheme 1). In grinding method we have used $\text{Mg}(\text{HSO}_4)_2$ and in microwave irradiation montmorillonite KSF clay is used as catalyst.

X = C₆H₅-F, C₆H₅-Br, C₆H₅-Cl, C₆H₅-I, C₆H₅OCH₃, , C₆H₅; Y = COCH₃

- (i) Mg(HSO₄)₂ Grinding method/rt
- (ii) KSF or PTSA microwave irradiation
- (iii) Conventional method

Scheme 1

Montmorillonite KSF showed catalytic activity for chalcone or pyrazoline synthesis and has many advantages over catalysts like NaOH, KOH, such as ease of handling, low cost and elimination of metal wastes. The microwave procedure for the synthesis of compounds (3a-

f) owes its importance due to the fact that the reaction is complete within 1-3 min as compared to conventional method which required 6-8 h (Tables 1 and 2). Purity of all new synthesized compounds was monitored by silica gel G coated TLC plates in various solvent systems.

Spermicidal activity : Four representative compounds (2a, 3a, 2d, 3d) were screened for their spermicidal activity. Testing was done on cryopreserved semen of HF cattle and Murrah buffalo. The motility of sperm was observed under 40 x magnification of light microscope in a cell counting chamber. 25 μL Solution in ethanol (100 ppm)²¹ of a compound was added to 25 μL of semen and motility of sperm was observed at different times after

Table 1. Spermicidal activity

Compd.	Dose (ppm)	Mortality (%)	Time (min)
2a	100	20	8
2d	100	5	3
3a	100	40	10
3d	100	80	10

Table 2. Characterization data, reaction time and yield of compounds 2a-f under solvent free method and conventional method

Compd.	X	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Melting point (°C)	Yield (%)			Time required		
					I	II	III	I min	II s	III min
2a	4-FC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ F ₂ O	294	65	67.0	66.5	65.0	9	180	60
2b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ClFO	310.5	93	68.0	65.0	64.0	10	190	45
2c	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ BrFO	354.9	113	62.0	63.0	66.5	10	140	50
2d	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ FO ₂	306	84	78.0	75.2	77.5	8	110	45
2e	Furfuryl	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ FO ₂	266	88	85.0	81.0	80.0	15	160	60
2f	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ FO	276	78	89.0	93.0	90.0	12	110	45

Note : All compounds gave C and H analysis within ±0.5 of the theoretical value.

(I) Grinding method, (II) Microwave irradiation, (III) Conventional method.

incubation. Compound **2d** reduced sperm motility below 20% when employed at 100 ppm concentration for 8 min. Compound **2a** exhibits more pronounced effect over the sperm motility as compared to **2d** putting all the sperm to rest within 3 min. Compound **3a** reduced motility to below 40% when employed at 100 ppm concentration for 10 min on the other hand, sperm motility was observed till 10 min after addition of **3d**.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open glass capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 grating infrared spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. PMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrophotometer (200 MHz) using CDCl_3 as a solvent. TMS was used as internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on Kratos 30 and 50 mass spectrometer. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel G as adsorbent in solvents of varying polarity.

General method for synthesis of 1-(4-fluoronaphthyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-propen-1-one (2a) :

Grinding method : A mixture of 4-fluoroacetophenone (3 mmol) and $\text{Mg}(\text{HSO}_4)_2$ (0.4 g) was grinded together in a mortar using a pestle to generate different colour. Then fluorinated aldehyde (3 mmol) was added to it and grinding continued for 10–25 min. Reaction proceeds exothermically indicated by the rise in temperature (5–8 °C). After the reaction was complete (when no starting material was detected by TLC analysis), CH_2Cl_2 was added and mixture was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and the solid thus obtained was purified by recrystallisation from ethyl alcohol to afford pure desired compound (**2a**).

Microwave-assisted solvent free synthesis of 2a : 4-Fluoroacetophenone (3 mmol) fluorinated aldehyde (3 mmol) and montmorillonite KSF (0.4 g) were thoroughly mixed in a pestle mortar. This mixture was then transferred into a 100 ml conical flask and irradiated with microwaves for 50–190 s (as indicated in Table 2) at 60 watts. After reaction was complete (indicated by absence of starting material in TLC) ethanol was added and mixture was filtered. The filtrate was recrystallised from ethanol to afford dark yellow crystals of desired compound (**2a**).

Conventional method : 4-Fluoroacetophenone (3 mmol) and fluorinated aldehyde (3 mmol) were dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol and then stirred at room temperature for about 15 min. Sufficient 2 N NaOH solution was added to it to make the solution with continuous stirring for about 30 min till a yellow precipitate was formed. This was then neutralized with 2 N HCl and diluted with water and left overnight. The precipitated chalcone was filtered washed well with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

The spectral data of synthesized compound (**2a**) are mentioned below : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O highly conjugated); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 7.5 (d, $\text{C}_\alpha\text{-H}$) and 7.7 (d, $\text{C}_\beta\text{-H}$) and 6.5–8.0 (complex multiplet aromatic protons).

All the other compounds (Table 2) were prepared by similar method and their characterization data and comparative data of various procedures are tabulated in Table 2.

General method for 1-acetyl-3-(4-fluoronaphthyl)-5-(4-fluorophenyl)-4H[4,5]pyrazoline :

Microwave-assisted solvent free synthesis : 4-Fluoroaldehyde (3 mmol), hydrazine hydrate/phenylhydrazine and appropriate amount of glacial acetic acid was taken in a 100 ml conical flask and then reaction mixture was irradiated inside the microwave oven at 40% power for 30–60 s. The reaction mixture was liquified and then PTSA was added as catalyst. Again irradiated 30–60 s. After the reaction was complete (indicated by absence of starting material in TLC) ethanol was added and mixture was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and crude product obtained and recrystallised from ethanol.

Conventional method : A mixture of 4-fluoroaldehyde (3 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (3 mmol) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h, the mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resultant solid mass was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

ν_{\max} 2800–2900 (CH_2), 1635, 1665 (C=O, C=N), 1100–1400 cm^{-1} (=C-F); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 2.4 (COCH_3), 3.2–3.6 (dd, CH_2), 5.6 (C-H) and 6.5–8.0 (complex multiplet aromatic protons).

All the other compounds (Table 3) were prepared by similar method and characteristics data and comparative data of various procedures are tabulated in Table 3.

Table 3. Characterization data, reaction time and yield of compounds (3a-f) by solvent free method and conventional method

Compd.	X	Y	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Melting point (°C)	Yield (%)		Time required	
						I	II	I s	II h
3a	F-C ₆ H ₄	COCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ F ₂ N ₂ O	350	65	89.0	87.0	70	6-8
3b	Cl-C ₆ H ₄	COCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClFN ₂ O	366.5	83	80.0	79.0	90	6-8
3c	Br-C ₆ H ₄	COCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ BrFN ₂ O	410.9	98	84.0	85.0	60	6-8
3d	OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	COCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ FN ₂ O	362	89	90.0	87.0	65	6-8
3e	Furfuryl	COCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O	332	105	79.0	83.0	70	6-8
3f	C ₆ H ₅	COCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O	332	80	85.0	88.0	60	6-8

Note : All compounds gave C and H analysis within ± 0.5 of the theoretical value.

(I) By microwave irradiation with PTSA reaction were carried out in an Samsung m 1630 N/M 1610 W household microwave oven with maximum 600 W power, (II) by conventional method.

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